

DESCRIPTION OF THE FREQUENCY OF DETECTION OF THE MAIN CLINICAL SYNDROMES OF CHOLECYSTITIS IN THE GERONT-SUPERGERONT POPULATION OF THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Relevance and necessity of the topic. From the results of the research conducted in Uzbekistan, it is known that 6 syndromes dominate the clinical presentation of cholecystitis in the geront and supergeront population: pain syndrome or feeling, dyspeptic syndrome, cholecystocardial syndrome, neurotic syndrome, vegetodystonia syndrome and allergic syndrome.

It is known that chronic cholecystitis often occurs against the background of comorbidity and changes its clinical picture depending on it. In this process, in different regions and population groups, specific characteristics appear. The results of this content were given in the research [1;2;3;4;].

The aim of the research is to study and determine the epidemiological, clinical and preventive characteristics of cholecystitis in the young, middle-aged, geront and supergeront populations of different regions of Uzbekistan.

Materials and research methods. This research is considered a simultaneous epidemiological investigation and it is based on the analysis of the results obtained in a population of 2682 people. Residents of 6 regions of the country - Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Jizzakh, Syrdarya and Kashkadarya - were involved in the study. Based on the tasks set in the work, 6 simultaneous epidemiological studies were organized and carried out in the valley and oasis regions of Uzbekistan.

A detailed description of the organization and conduct of the epidemiological study was provided: the screening group was formed, questionnaires were prepared, and the screening group was introduced to the necessary equipment for the study. A procedure for working with the population was created and a procedure for checking the population was developed.

Results and Discussions. In determining the main clinical syndromes of chronic cholecystitis in the geront and supergeront population of the Fergana Valley, it was confirmed that the weight share (n=68/0) in the geront population with chronic cholecystitis - 49.6% (chronic cholecystitis without stones - 13.5% and chronic cholecystitis with stones - 36.1) and in the supergeront population - 100.0% (stoneless chronic cholecystitis - 100.0% and stone chronic cholecystitis

- 0.00%) is observed with detection frequencies (RR=0.496; 95% CI=0.418 - 5.589; $\chi^2=2.000$; S= 0.121; P>0.05).

Dyspeptic syndrome (n=11) in the geront population with chronic cholecystitis of the valley is confirmed with a prevalence of 8.3%.

Dyspeptic syndrome is confirmed by the detection frequency of non-stone type of chronic cholecystitis - 6.0% and stone type - 2.3%. Not recorded in the supergeront population (0.00%).

Cholecystocardial syndrome (n=9) is detected in geront and supergeront population with chronic cholecystitis in 6.8% and 0.00% respectively.

The prevalence of this syndrome is 1.5% in chronic cholecystitis without stones and 5.3% in chronic cholecystitis with stones.

The next characteristic clinical presentation is considered to be the manifestation of neurotic syndrome in high frequencies for chronic cholecystitis in valley conditions. For example, it was observed that neurotic syndrome with chronic cholecystitis is recorded in the geront population with a frequency of 20.3%, chronic cholecystitis without stones - 15.0% and chronic cholecystitis with stones - 5.3%. In the supergeront population, the neurotic syndrome is expressed in a frequency of 50.0% (50.0% in chronic cholecystitis without stones and 0.00% in chronic cholecystitis with stones) (RR=0.406; 95% CI=0.097 - 1.690; $\chi^2= 1.057$; S=0.088; P>0.05).

Vegetodystonia (n=18) in the geront population with SX - 12.0% (in chronic cholecystitis without stones - 8.3% and in chronic cholecystitis with stones - 3.8%) and in the supergeront population - 100.0% (in chronic cholecystitis without stones - 100.0% and in stone chronic cholecystitis - from 0.00%) is confirmed in detection frequencies (RR=0.120; 95% CI=0.076 - 0.190; $\chi^2=13.195$; S=0.298; P<0.001).

Allergic syndrome (n=4) is noted with a frequency of 3.0% in the geront population with chronic cholecystitis, its non-stone type - 3.0% and non-stone type - 0.00%. Not recorded in supergeronts.

Conclusion. It can be concluded that these data are of prognostic, clinical, preventive and therapeutic value for the geront-supergeront population of the valley.

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